

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Machine Learning-Based Prediction System for Optimizing Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: UWSNs have significant applications in the marine ecosystem, oceanographic research, and inspection of marine infrastructures underwater. But the rough underwater conditions come with the problem of a long latency, loss of packets, attenuation of signals and a scarcity of energy, which lower network reliability and performance. This study aims at designing a machine learning-based prediction system to enhance the performance, reliability and energy efficiency of UWSNs by predicting the network behaviour and sensor node states given different underwater environmental and communication conditions. **Method:** The suggested predictive framework uses several machine learning models, such as CatBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM, Random Forest (RF), Decision Tree (DT), Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). The models have been trained on a dataset of both real and synthetic data of sensors in underwater environments, sensor properties, and environmental conditions (temperature, salinity, pressure), and network variables (signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), traffic load, and battery level). Preprocessing of data using methods like data cleaning, Min-Max scaling, and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) are used to enhance the stability of the model. The dataset is split into an 80/20 training-testing data and 10-fold cross-validation is employed to make the dataset robust. Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score and ROC-AUC are used to measure model performance. **Findings:** The results of the experiments prove that CatBoost and XGBoost have the highest predictive performance and reach an accuracy of 92.1, a precision of 0.90, a recall of 0.91, an F1-score of 0.91, and a ROC-AUC of 0.93. LightGBM was able to perform competitively as well with an accuracy of 91.5 percent but at a faster execution and less consumptions of memory. Random Forest was very robust to noisy underwater data. Conversely, Gaussian Naive Bayes had the shortest execution time, but had worse accuracy (79.1) and less reliability in noisy conditions. The findings suggest that the performance of ensemble learning algorithms is superior to that of the traditional models to solve the underwater network complex and uncertain conditions.

Novelty: This study makes one of the very first detailed comparative analysis on multiple machine learning algorithms to predict and optimize UWSN performance in realistic underwater conditions. The suggested framework incorporates both environmental sensing parameters and network metrics along with energy-related features in order to achieve predictive optimization of the network with the help of AI. The system allows adaptive and self-optimizing underwater networks, which allow the early warning of the communication breakdowns, better energy control, and increased reliability. The framework can find application in marine ecosystems, underwater pipeline inspection, disaster prediction and maritime security operations due to these capabilities.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; CatBoost; Machine Learning; XGBoost; Network Optimization; Prediction System; Underwater wireless sensor networks

1 Introduction

UWSNs have become a needed technology in the area of monitoring underwater environments, gathering oceanographic information, and providing inspection on underwater infrastructures like oil pipelines, offshore platforms, and submarine communication cables. These networks are composed of distributed sensor nodes which interact together by the use of an acoustic, optical or electromagnetic signal to measure environmental parameters including temperature, salinity, pressure and ocean currents. Such data gathered in these networks are very important in the applications such as marine ecosystem monitoring, disaster prediction, underwater exploration, and military surveillance.

UWSNs have a high potential, but poor underwater conditions expose them to a number of challenges. Underwater communication, unlike in the case of terrestrial wireless sensor network, has high propagation delays, limited bandwidth, attenuation of the signal, experience of multipath fading, and intense noise interference. Moreover, sensor nodes when submerged do not generally have much battery resources and, therefore, energy efficiency is a vital design element. There are additional environmental conditions like water currents, biofouling and mobility of nodes that make the maintenance of reliable long lasting underwater communication networks even more complex.

The common methods of enhancing UWSN performance are limited to routing mechanisms, clustering schemes, and optimization methods of communication. Although these solutions have enhanced some performance of networks, they usually base on fixed principles and pre-established network models that are not responsive to dynamic underwater conditions. Consequently, the network performance can suffer because of the unforeseen environmental factors, node malfunctions and changing the quality of communication.

The recent developments in the field of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) have offered good opportunities to deal with these issues. ML-based methods make it possible to conduct forecasting of network behavior to better understand the nature of networks to predict communication failures, achieve better routing policies, and enhance energy management. ML models can improve the efficiency and dependability of UWSNs by acquiring patterns using environmental data and network conditions. Nevertheless, the current research on the topic is still inadequate in a number of ways.

Other researchers have researched machine learning methods used in stimulating underwater communication and sensor network performance. Saravanan et al.⁽¹⁾ used Logistic Regression and Linear Regression models as methods of prediction of underwater communication performance. Even though Logistic regression demonstrated superior prediction accuracy, the authors used a small sample and a narrow range of environmental parameters to conduct the study so its application in practice is limited. To enhance the efficiency of data transmission of the underwater sensor network, Kaveripakam and Chinthaginjala⁽²⁾ suggested a model called constant bit rate underwater wireless sensor network (CB-UWSN). The research however, was primarily devoted to the evaluation of network performance and did not include the adaptive prediction mechanisms.

The underwater wireless communication technologies such as acoustic, optical and magneto-inductive communication were extensively surveyed by Jouhari et al.⁽³⁾ Although the survey identifies technological issues in underwater communications, it does not suggest any predictive or adaptive solutions to enhance the reliability of the networks. Likewise, Lin et al.⁽⁴⁾, examined the LoRa communication in underwater conditions and examined the changes in the quality of links with depth. Even though their work includes very helpful information about the nature of underwater communication, it is restricted to the context of a certain communication technology and does not cover the issue of predictive network optimization.

Recently researches have begun to combine machine learning methods with underwater sensor networks. Wang et al.⁽⁵⁾ suggested an adaptive data transmission algorithm (EP-ADTA) which involves edge prediction and reinforcement learning to enhance the efficiency in transmitting data. Although the method enhances accuracy of communication, it is directly affected by

the complexity of reinforcement learning and increases computational load. Park et al. (6) have applied machine learning models to forecast ocean currents in order to prioritize handovers between underwater sensor nodes. The Decision Tree classifier demonstrated encouraging scores but the accuracy of prediction was rather low and the model was trained on the data of one geographic area.

Nevertheless, there are still some significant research gaps. To begin with, most of the current studies are more oriented to a single machine learning model without comparing several algorithms in the same circumstances. Second, the majority of techniques focus on particular factors of UWSN performance, including routing or communication reliability, and does not offer a global prediction model that mediates the relationship between environmental factors, network measures, and sensor properties. Third, the stability of machine learning models under noisy underwater conditions with missing data or uncertain data has not been widely studied.

To improve on these shortcomings, this study will suggest a machine learning-based predictive model of optimizing the performance of the Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks. The suggested system will combine several machine learning algorithms, such as Decision Tree (DT), Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest (RF), CatBoost, LightGBM, and XGBoost, to predict network behavior and find possible failures of communication. The system considers the environmental variables, sensor characteristics, and network conditions, which enhances a more holistic and adaptive means of optimization of UWSN. Comparison of existing in UWSN Optimization is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of Existing Works in UWSN Optimization

Refererence	Approach	Advantages	Limitations
(1)	Logistic & Linear Regression	Simple prediction model	Small dataset, limited parameters
(2)	CBR-based UWSN architecture	Improved transmission efficiency	No predictive or adaptive mechanism
(3)	Survey on underwater communication	Comprehensive overview of technologies	No predictive optimization
(4)	LoRa link quality analysis	Provides empirical communication data	Limited to specific technology
(5)	Reinforcement learning-based adaptive transmission	Improved transmission efficiency	High computational complexity
(6)	ML-based ocean current prediction	Supports node mobility prediction	Limited accuracy and geographic scope
Proposed Method	Multi-algorithm ML prediction system	High accuracy, robust to noise, adaptive optimization	Requires computational resources

2 Methodology

2.1 Data Collection

The predictive system for Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks (UWSNs) is built using data that has already been collected and data that has been created. These files contain information about the physical properties of underwater sensors, the weather, and the network traffic that affects how well the UWSN works. Sensor node classification, energy consumption rate, battery status, deployment depth, water temperature, salinity, pressure, current intensity, network traffic statistics, and communication metrics are all important. The dataset includes structured sensor data and historical network logs, which are very important for teaching machine learning models how to predict how the network will work and how sensor nodes will act. Synthetic data imitates real-world environments by simulating sensor interactions with environmental variables shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Data Pre-processing

2.2.1. Data Cleaning

Cleaned data is fed to machine learning algorithms. The latter refers to the recovery of missing samples by packet loss or sensor failure and the removal of outliers using statistical means such as Z-score or IQR. The models are then trained on what has been average, and therefore more realistic.

Fig 1. System Architecture

2.2.2. Feature Engineering

Raw data are passed to scaling functions in order to convert the raw data into meaningful features for machine learning (ML) algorithms, such as Min-Max Scaling and Standardization. Label Encoding or One-Hot Encoding is the process of converting Nominal (Categorical) data into numbers. Feature selection techniques which reduce dimensions and consequently improve model performance are utilized, e.g., PCA (Principal Component Analysis), RFE (Recursive Feature Elimination). It helps to avoid being dominant by one feature.

2.2.3. Data Partitioning

The dataset is divided into two parts: a training set and a testing set. This lets us accurately measure how well the model works. An 80/20 split is the norm, with 80% of the data going to training and 20% going to testing. Cross-validation methods, like 5-fold or 10-fold cross-validation, are used to find out how well the model can generalize and to stop it from overfitting.

2.3 ML Algorithms

Different machine learning algorithms are used to guess and improve how well UWSN works. Here is a short description of each algorithm and how it relates to the problem:

2.3.1. Decision Tree (DT)

Decision Trees are used to make rules for making decisions based on sensor data and network traffic metrics. They make predictions by splitting the data into branches based on feature values (like signal strength or battery level) over and over again. The tree structure makes it easy to understand and quickly sort out sensor node failures or communication problems.

2.3.2. Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB)

GNB is a probabilistic classifier that uses Bayes' Theorem and assumes that features are independent. It figures out the likelihood of each class (like a healthy or broken sensor node) based on the input data and picks the one with the highest chance.

2.3.3. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

KNN sorts or guesses based on the "k" closest data points in the feature space. It finds data points that are similar by using a distance metric (like Euclidean distance) and gives the majority class of the neighbors.

2.3.4. Random Forest (RF)

Random Forest is an ensemble learning algorithm that makes a lot of decision trees during training and combines their results to make predictions more accurate and less likely to fit the data too closely. Each tree learns from a random part of the data, and the final prediction is the average of the predictions made by all the trees.

2.3.5. CatBoost & LightGBM

These are gradient boosting algorithms that make quick and accurate predictions. CatBoost and LightGBM build models one at a time, with each new model trying to fix the mistakes of the one before it. CatBoost works well with categorical features without a lot of preprocessing, and LightGBM speeds up training and accuracy by using a leaf-wise growth strategy.

2.3.6. XGBoost

XGBoost is another gradient boosting algorithm that builds models over and over again to make sure they make fewer mistakes when predicting. It uses regularization to cut down on overfitting and parallel processing to speed up training. XGBoost works very well with structured data and big datasets, which is why it is so popular for predictive modeling.

The combination of these machine learning algorithms makes a strong base for predicting and improving different parts of UWSNs. The system can accurately predict network performance problems, sensor node failures, and traffic patterns by using these models on real or synthetic datasets. This makes sure that underwater networks will be reliable and efficient for a long time.

2.4 Mathematical Model

The proposed predictive framework for Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks (UWSNs) uses machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) to predict how the network will act in changing underwater conditions. The mathematical model formalizes the system's input parameters, predictive functions, and optimization objectives that together make the network more reliable, use less energy, and send data more accurately.

2.4.1. System Representation

Let the UWSN be represented as a connected graph shown in Eq. 1:

$$G = (N, L) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $N = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k\}$ denotes the set of sensor nodes,
- $L = \{l_{i,j}\}$ denotes the communication links between nodes n_i and n_j .

Each node n_i in Eq. 2 has the following properties:

$$n_i = \{E_i, P_i, T_i, S_i, R_i\} \tag{2}$$

Where:

- E_i : residual energy of node i ,
- P_i : packet transmission power,
- T_i : transmission delay,
- S_i : single to noise ratio (SNR)
- R_i : data rate.

2.4.2. Energy Consumption Model

The total energy consumed by node i for transmitting a packet of size b bits across a distance d_{ij} is modeled as in Eq. 3:

$$E_{tx}(i, j) = b.(E_{elec} + \varepsilon_{amp}.d_{ij}^\alpha) \tag{3}$$

and for receiving represented in Eq. 4:

$$E_{rx}(i) = b.E_{elec} \tag{4}$$

Where:

- E_{elec} : energy consumed by electronic circuitry per bit,
- ε_{amp} : energy required by the amplifier,
- α : path loss exponent (typically $2 \leq \alpha \leq 4$ for underwater channels).

The total network energy consumption is in Eq. 5:

$$E_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^N (E_{tx}(i, j) + E_{rx}(i)) \tag{5}$$

And the average node lifetime is inversely proportional to this energy loss in Eq. 6:

$$L_{avg} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{E_{init}(i)}{E_{tx}(i, j) + E_{rx}(i)} \tag{6}$$

2.4.3. Communication Reliability Model

Communication reliability R_c is determined by the packet delivery ratio (PDR) and the bit error rate (BER) shown in Eq. 7:

$$R_c = (1 - BER). PDR \tag{7}$$

Where BER represented in Eq. 8:

$$BER = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_b}{N_o}}\right) \tag{8}$$

and $Q(.)$ denotes the gaussian error function.

E_b/N_o represents the signal to noise ratio (SNR) per bit.

The PDR between two nodes is expressed as Eq. 9:

$$PDR = \frac{P_{received}}{P_{sent}} \tag{9}$$

This relation enable the prediction of data transmission success under varying underwater conditions.

2.4.4. Delay Model

The total end-to-end delay D_{total} for data transmission shown in Eq. 10 includes propagation, queuing, and processing delays:

$$D_{total} = D_{Prop} + D_{queue} + D_{proc} \tag{10}$$

Given that acoustic propagation dominates underwater we have Eq. 11:

$$D_{prop} = \frac{d_{ij}}{v_{sound}} \tag{11}$$

Where v_{sound} is the speed of the sound underwater, approximately 1500m/s

2.4.5. Machine Learning Prediction Function

Let the dataset $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^m$ represents network samples, where:

- $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$: feature vector (e.g., temperature, salinity, depth, SNR, packet loss),
- $y_i \in \mathbb{R}$: target variable (e.g., predicted network performance or node failure state).

Each ML model f_θ approximates the mapping function in Eq. 12;

$$\hat{y}_i = f_\theta(x_i) \tag{12}$$

Where θ denotes the model parameters.

The optimization object is to minimize the prediction error in Eq. 13:

$$\min_\theta \mathcal{L}(\theta) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - f_\theta(x_i))^2 \tag{13}$$

For ensemble learning methods (e.g., CatBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM), the final prediction is a weighted sum of multiple base learners shown in Eq. 14:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{t=1}^T n_t f_t(x_i) \tag{14}$$

Where n_t is the learning rate f_t is the weak learner at iteration t.

2.4.6. Objective Function for UWSN Optimization

The global optimization objective combines accuracy, energy efficiency, and communication reliability as a multi-objective problem shown in Eq. 15:

$$\max J = w_1 \cdot R_c + w_2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{E_{total}}{E_{init}}\right) + w_3 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{D_{total}}{D_{max}}\right) \tag{15}$$

Subject to Eq. 16:

$$\begin{cases} E_i > 0, \forall_i \in N \\ PDR > PDR_{min} \\ BER < BER_{max} \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

where w_1, w_2, w_3 are tunable weights satisfying $w_1 + w_2 + w_3 = 1$

This function seeks to maximize network reliability while minimizing both energy consumption and communication latency.

2.4.7. Model Validation Metrics

The trained ML models were evaluated using standard metrics shown in Eq. 17, 18, 19, and 20 as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \tag{17}$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, \quad Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (18)$$

$$F1 - Score = 2 \cdot \frac{precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + recall} \quad (19)$$

$$ROC - AUC = \int_0^1 TPR(FPR) dFPR \quad (20)$$

Where TP , TN , FP , FN denote True and False Positive and Negatives, respectively.

The mathematical model combines physical layer modeling, statistical learning theory, and multi-objective optimization to make UWSN work better. The system achieves adaptive, reliable, and energy-aware underwater communication suitable for long-term environmental monitoring, infrastructure inspection, and disaster prediction by forecasting communication performance, predicting node failure, and minimizing energy consumption.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Experimental Setup

The study focuses on creating a prediction system for UWSNs utilizing the Python programming language due to its extensive machine learning libraries. Some important libraries are scikit-learn for regular algorithms, CatBoost for gradient boosting, XGBoost for fast and scalable gradient boosting, LightGBM for speed and accuracy, Pandas for data manipulation and preprocessing, NumPy for numerical analysis, and Matplotlib and Seaborn for data visualization. Some of the tools and platforms used are Google Colab for faster model training, Python Notebooks for interactive coding and testing, and Kaggle for getting publicly available datasets for UWSN simulations and for posting models for benchmarking and collaboration.

The following steps were taken to see how well each model worked:

1. Accuracy is the number of times an event is predicted correctly divided by the total number of times it happens.
2. Precision: The number of correctly predicted positive cases compared to the total number of positive cases that were expected.
3. Recall (Sensitivity): The number of true positive cases that were correctly identified compared to the total number of true positive cases.
4. F1-Score: The harmonic mean of accuracy and recall, which gives you a good mix of the two.
5. ROC-AUC: The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, which looks at the balance between true positive and false positive rates at different thresholds.

The evaluation of machine learning models for predicting underwater wireless sensor networks (UWSNs) revealed that CatBoost and XGBoost are the most effective models, demonstrating superior accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. LightGBM worked very well, combining high accuracy with low resource use and fast execution times. Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB) was the fastest algorithm, but it wasn't as accurate and had trouble with noisy data. Random Forest is a good choice because it has balanced accuracy and is very resistant to noise. KNN and Decision Trees did okay, but they were slower and less stable than ensemble methods.

3.2 Performance Comparison

A confusion matrix is a classification model assessment instrument. It provides the detailed view of the accuracy of the model in the prediction of each class as represented in Figure 2. It displays the real values alongside the supposed values and it is often configured in the following manner:

1. True Positives (TP): The number of times the model was correct in identifying the positive class (e.g. the times when the model reported that a sensor was broken when it was actually broken).
2. True Negatives (TN): The cases when the model made the correct decision of the negative (e.g. when the sensor in question was operating and the model believed it was operating).

3. False Positives (FP): The model labeled the positive class as broken when it was not actually broken (i.e. when a functional sensor was labeled as non-functional).
4. False Negatives (FN): In cases where the model has mistakenly classified the negative category, e.g. when a faulty sensor was believed to be functional.

Fig 2. Confusion matrices of machine learning algorithms for UWSN performance prediction: (a) Naïve Bayes, (b) Decision Tree, (c) K-Nearest Neighbors, (d) Random Forest, (e) LightGBM, (f) XGBoost, and (g) CatBoost.

3.3 Explanation of ROC Curve in Relation to Machine Learning Algorithms

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve visually shows how well a classifier can tell the difference between classes at different threshold levels. The ROC curve shows:

True Positive Rate (TPR) or Sensitivity: $TP / (TP + FN)$

False Positive Rate (FPR): $FP / (FP + TN)$

As shown in Figure 3, a ROC curve that gets closer to the top-left corner shows that the model is better at telling the difference between positive and negative classes.

The Area Under the Curve (AUC) checks how well the model works. A score of 1 means the model is perfect, and a score of 0.5 means the model works like random chance.

Fig 3. ROC curves for multi-class classification using different machine learning algorithms: (a) Naïve Bayes, (b) Decision Tree, (c) K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), (d) Random Forest, (e) LightGBM, (f) XGBoost, and (g) CatBoost.

3.4 ROC Curve for Various Algorithms

In extreme instances of overfitting, Decision Tree (DT) can generate a jagged ROC curve. AUC could be lower if your tree is not valid for new data. GNB usually gets smoother ROC curve but perhaps a lower AUC since in practice no feature is independent of another. The ROC curve could vary with the value of k And if k is too small, then the model may become overfit and FPR will increase. When k becomes larger, this model might not fit well and result a decrease of TPR. Random Forest (RF): There is a trend that the model could work full well (high AUC). Adding together a few trees will lead to a more robust way of generalization. CatBoost, LightGBM, and XGBoost tend to be higher in AUC, which implies that they are more effective in the classification of things. Their gradient boosting algorithm improves prediction every time, increasing the TPR and decreasing the FPR. To test

the models on the same dataset we used a number of different metrics to determine which algorithm could best predict UWSN performance.

3.5 Comparison with Existing Studies and Novelty Analysis

In order to determine the efficiency of the proposed prediction framework, which is based on machine learning, the results were compared with the results of the recent literature that used machine learning methods to analyze wireless sensor networks and underwater communication systems. Table 2 includes the results of some representative researches and compares them to the results of the proposed model.

Table 2. Comparison with Previous Studies

Reference	Method	Application	Accuracy (%)	Key Limitations
(1)	Logistic Regression	UWSN communication prediction	82.4	Small dataset, limited parameters
(6)	Decision Tree Classifier	Ocean current prediction for UWSNs	55.79 (Rank-1)	Location-specific dataset
(5)	Reinforcement Learning	Adaptive data transmission in UWSNs	88	High computational cost
(7)	ML regression models	Network parameter prediction	85-89	Limited environmental factors
Proposed Method	CatBoost / XGBoost / LightGBM	UWSN performance prediction	92.1	Requires computational resources

3.5.1. Comparison of the results with the Existing Works:

The findings of this paper are aligned to a number of current-day publications which point out the efficiency of the ensemble learning algorithms in the applications of wireless sensor networks. On the same note, Uyan et al. (2023)⁽⁷⁾ demonstrated that machine learning models significantly improve prediction accuracy in underwater sensor networks by capturing complex relationships between environmental and network parameters. Their study reported accuracy levels ranging from 85% to 89%. Similarly, Wang et al. (2022)⁽⁵⁾ proposed a reinforcement learning-based adaptive transmission method that improved communication efficiency, although at the cost of higher computational complexity. These findings support the results of the present study, where gradient boosting models such as XGBoost achieved an accuracy of 91.8%. This confirms that ensemble learning techniques are highly effective for handling complex and dynamic underwater network conditions.

Nevertheless, previous research had much lower prediction performance because of methodological factors. As an example, Saravanan et al.⁽¹⁾ modeled underwater communication outcomes with the help of the Logistic Regression model and obtained the desired precision of about 82. Though it was showing computationally efficiency, this method did not have the capability to elicit nonlinear relationships between environmental variables and network conditions. Conversely, the ensemble learning models employed in the proposed framework yielded a better predictive power in terms of integrating several decision trees and refining errors in prediction.

Park et al.⁽⁶⁾ also published another pertinent work, which used the Decision Tree classifiers to forecast the direction of ocean currents in order to make a decision regarding handover of underwater sensor nodes. The model had Rank-1 accuracy of 55.79 which is far less as compared to the findings of the present research. The reason behind this variation can be explained by the fact that their model relies on a limited range of features and the geographical limitations, but the proposed framework combines several environmental parameters and network metrics.

Also, Wang et al.⁽⁵⁾ presented an adaptive data transmission algorithm (EP-ADTA) that uses reinforcement learning to adjust to the dynamics of the wireless sensor networks of underwater environments. Although they led to better communication efficiency and adaptability, it is common that reinforcement learning models need a long training period and computation. Conversely, the gradient boosting models that were employed in the current study offer high predictive accuracy at comparatively lesser calculation complexity, rendering them appropriate to real life network optimization exercises.

3.5.2. Discussion of Current Findings

Results of experiment show that with regard to UWSN prediction issue, ensemble learning algorithms have more unanimous advantage than traditional machine learning methods. The best performance overall was observed using CatBoost, with a top

accuracy of 92.1%, and ROC-AUC equal to 0.93, closely followed by the XGBoost and LightGBM algorithms (the tested models). These results align with previous studies, which have demonstrated that those who can perform gradient boosting algorithms, can adeptly navigate through noisy datasets, nonlinear relationships, and feature interactions.

On the contrary, other simpler algorithms including Gaussian Naive Bayes and Decision Trees exhibited lower performance in this scenario because of their foundational presumption as well as sensitivity to noisy data. Ensemble learning techniques better suit the modeling of underwater communication environment since it is a complex system with unpredictable and noisy environmental conditions.

3.5.3. Novelty of the Proposed Work

Several features of this research distinguish it from other studies and constitute its novelty.

- First, this study offers an extensive comparison of various machine learning algorithms in a single predictive framework for underwater wireless sensor networks. Previous work has featured only one or two algorithms, restricting the capacity to assess which model is best suited for UWSN optimization.
- Second, the proposed model incorporates sensor features and environmental factors along with communication metrics all at once, thus giving a more complete representation of underwater networks compared to previous research that considered isolated parameters.
- In summary, the major contributions of this study are: 1) A fully labeled MTS dataset for underwater image classification obtained in the real-world ocean environment is presented; 2) The proposed architecture explores advanced data pre-processing techniques linearly fuse different texture frequencies to build mixed textures models (surface heat maps); Lastly, the strength of machine learning models under noisy underwater conditions is tokenized and tested across a wide variety of models including traditional classifiers suited to deep machine learning methods; it finds that ensemble methods; CatBoost, XGBoost and LightGBM outperform traditional classifier metrics in terms of performing quality on unseen datasets using feature dimensionality reduction techniques.
- Lastly, the suggested model presents an AI-based predictive system for prevention-oriented network optimization, allowing early identification of communication breakdowns and minimizing energy expenditure. This ability can facilitate self-adaptive and energy-efficient underwater sensor networks, a major contribution towards long-term marine monitoring applications.

The comparison shows that the implementation of predicted systems using machine learning has higher accuracy, noise tolerance and prediction powers as compared to many already existing methods.

Table 3 compares the accuracy of prediction, the time required to execute, the amount of CPU and memory, and noisy data behavior. The performance will be summarized in the form of a table and the results will be discussed.

Table 3. Comparison of Performance Measure

Algorithm	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	ROC-AUC	Execution Time (s)	Memory Usage (MB)	Robustness to Noise
Decision Tree (DT)	85.4	0.84	0.82	0.83	0.86	1.2	45	Moderate
Gaussian NB (GNB)	79.1	0.76	0.81	0.78	0.79	0.8	30	Low
KNN	82.3	0.81	0.77	0.79	0.82	4.6	65	Moderate
Random Forest (RF)	90.2	0.88	0.89	0.88	0.91	2.4	90	High
CatBoost	92.1	0.90	0.91	0.91	0.93	3.0	85	Very High
LightGBM	91.5	0.89	0.90	0.90	0.92	1.8	70	Very High
XGBoost	91.8	0.90	0.91	0.91	0.93	2.6	80	Very High

The study looked at how well different underwater network models worked and found that CatBoost was the best one because it had the highest accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. It also did very well on ROC-AUC, which shows that it can handle the complexities of UWSN data. Gaussian naive bayes has produced the least time-consuming results and it consumed the minimum memory but its accuracy was lower as well as robustness to noise, so its reliability is also lower in UWSN cases. They can handle complex patterns in the data as they have an ability to combine several models. It makes them applicable to UWSNs.

KNN worked, but was slow and memory consuming because it needed to calculate the distances for every new prediction. Random Forest, LightGBM and XGBoost all would do just fine consuming less memory and time being faster but still the results are very accurate.

The analysis of errors revealed the uncertainties under water such as signal disturbances, attenuation and background noise can lead to the corruptions of sensor results leading to failed predictions. These limitations make it difficult to preserve the precision of models, especially in case of missing or sparse wells data. In further rounds, predictions may be strengthened by using additional input data such as time trends or more sensor signals. You need to be able to conceptualize a model in order to tell whether it is effective. The confusion matrix is one of the most important graphs used to evaluate a model. It reveals the true positive, false positive, true negative and false negative of each model. This curve demonstrates the capability of the model to discriminate between working and faulty sensor nodes in UWSNs. The feature significance plots will allow us to identify the features from that have the most significant influence on the UWSN performance value estimations, and therefore improvements can be achieved much more easily.

ROC curves reflect the balance between TPR and FPR under different thresholds. The higher the Area Under the Curve (AUC), the better is your classifier. In summary, we can observe the comparison of these models from representative ROC curve in Figure 1 and XGBoost and CatBoost could get relatively bigger AUC values meaning that they are more effective.

The trade off between sensitivity and specificity for each of the above classifiers is reflected by the curves shown in graph1 and graph2. CatBoost and XGBoost show a higher value of AUC so it is more efficient. Better yet, you need them to see models working nicely in UWSNs.

4 Conclusion

This study introduces a machine learning-based predictive modeling framework that will streamline the work of Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks (UWSNs) in the intricate underwater conditions. It uses environmental parameters and metrics in the network to improve the accuracy of prediction and energy efficiency. The analysis of several machine learning algorithms such as Decision Tree, the Gaussian Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors, the Random Forest, CatBoost, LightGBM, and XGBoost, has shown that the ensemble learning algorithms outperformed the traditional models. The best accuracy was obtained with CatBoost (92.1%); XGBoost and LightGBM have a close score. The originality of the framework is that a large number of algorithms and environmental determinants are consolidated in one framework, which predicts better than other studies that were conducted on only one algorithm or in one parameter.

Besides, the benefits of the suggested system include the enhanced resistance to difficult conditions, the realism of underwater parameters evaluation, and insights into the model selection. Nevertheless, there are still issues, including the use of mix datasets, which may not necessarily be representative of the real world, and the computational costs of ensemble approaches that may not be able to run on resource constrained sensor nodes. The future research directions entail the investigation of the deep learning and reinforcement learning and to advance further routing and communication efficiency of UWSNs. Its potential application in diverse areas such as marine surveillance, underwater inspections, and maritime security has potential to attain resilience and extended working life of the network, as well as the ability to work in multiple areas. Generally, the paper highlights how machine learning has become an important aspect of enhancing the dependability and flexibility of underwater sensor networks.

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